

Adhesive Strength of Endodontic Sealer Epoxy Resin with Addition of Nano Chitosan High Molecular in Root Canals

Gari Wijaya¹, Trimurni Abidin¹, Dennis,¹ Harry Agusnar,² Basri A. Gani³

¹ Department of Conservative Dentistry, Faculty of Dentistry, Universitas Sumatera Utara Medan, Indonesia

² Departemen of Chemistry, Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Science, Universitas Sumatera Utara, Medan, Indonesia

³ Department of Oral Biology, Dentistry faculty, Universitas Syiah Kuala, Darussalam, Banda Aceh, Aceh, Indonesia

Abstract:- Root canal treatment is performed to repair and increase the resilience of the tooth. Using a suitable sealer material can increase penetration and adhesion to the root canal wall. Epoxy and chitosan resins have been reported to act as endodontic sealers with good penetration and adhesive properties. The evaluation of the penetration and adhesion properties of epoxy resin sealer and nano chitosan high molecular on the tubules dentin in root canal. The absorption and penetration assay of sealer used to the methylene blue dye assessment, while the confirmation the adhesive strength using SEM (Scanning electron microscope). The addition of chitosan nanoparticles 1% allowed the epoxy sealer group to have better penetration and absorption capabilities in tooth root canals. In addition, this group increased the adhesion of the root canal wall compared to other groups because it increased its density and adapted well to the entire dentine tubules on the root canal wall. The sealer penetration value was significantly different between the treatment groups ($p < 0.005$); 0.001) with a strong relationship ($r = 0.89$). Epoxy resin sealer with the addition of 1% chitosan high molecule nanoparticle has excellent absorption and penetration properties in root canal walls, increasing adhesion to root canal walls.

Keywords:- Adhesive, Chitosan, Root Canal, Sealer Endodontic.

I. INTRODUCTION

Root canal treatment highly depends on the endodontic triad (Access, Clean & Shape, Obturation). Root canal treatment has a high level of difficulty because it is difficult to observe the shape of the root canal. At the filling stage of the root canal system, guttapercha is used as the primary obturation material, which is applied with an endodontic sealer, which functions as a material to cover the gap that exists between the guttapercha and the treated root canal (Tabassum and Khan, 2016). The density between the sealer and the root canal wall is significant to know microscopically because the success of root canal treatment is also influenced by the sealing ability of the filling material to the dentine tubules of the root canal to binding of dentine collagen and its penetration in dentine tubules (Mamootil and Messer, 2007).

In endodontic treatment, root canal obturation/filling aims to prevent recontamination of root canals filled with guttapercha as the primary filling material and endodontic sealer (Jin et al., 2021). The endodontic sealer acts as a lubricant and assists in compacting the filling by bonding the guttapercha to the dentinal walls and filling any voids that the primary filling material cannot load. The success of endodontic treatment in the long term depends on the solid filling after root canal obturation (Al-Askary et al., 2013). The failure of sealer penetration can lead to the development of *Enterococcus faecalis*, *fusobacterium nucleatum*, *Actinobacillus actinomycetemcomitans*, which can interfere with sealer density and endodontic treatment failure (Huang et al., 2018 and Darmawi et al. 2022).

Dimensional changes and failure of sealer adhesion with guttapercha are the main problems in increasing the reliability of the root canal surface. Therefore, the adaptability of sealers to dentin is a significant factor in micro fissures and root canal reinfection (Russell, 2017). Roth (2011) reported that sealers based on epoxy resin did not experience volumetric shrinkage (shrinkage) during the polymerization process compared to sealers based on methacrylate. Epoxy sealers have disadvantages such as polymerization that lasts 24-36 hours, contains silver powder, causes tooth discoloration, and is highly cytotoxic to fibroblast cells (Roth, 2011).

Chitosan is a natural ingredient consisting of glucosamine and N-acetyl-glucosamine. In general, Chitosan is biocompatible, non-toxic, biodegradable, and antibacterial. In dental conservation, high molecular Chitosan has been developed, which has been applied to reversible pulpitis, antibacterial, and endodontic regeneration (Adiana et al., 2018). Sutrisman et al. (2013) reported the addition of high molecular chitosan nanoparticles with a weight of 0.015% w/v in the glass ionomer variant (SIKMR and SIKMRn) was able to increase the attachment between the material to dentin (Sutrisman et al., 2013).

The application of an epoxy resin sealer is expected to increase penetration into the dentinal tubules and seal all ramifications and dentinal tubules in the apical 1/3 of the root. The combination of an epoxy resin sealer with the addition of high molecular chitosan nanoparticles is expected to increase the adhesive power to the root canal wall.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

A. Research Materials

The study used premolar Teeth and Epoxy resin as a sealer material. The divided in three groups (Sealer Epoxy resin (AH Plus) as control, Sealer Epoxy resin + nano chitosan high molecule 1%, and sealer epoxy resin + nano chitosan high molecule 2%. Also used to the irrigation of NaOCl 2,5 % + EDTA 17% as control, Irrigation of NaCl 2.5 % + nano chitosan high molecule 0.1%, Irrigation of NaCl 2.5 % + nano chitosan high molecule 0.2%. These materials were then assessed for absorption and penetration properties in the dentine tubules of the root canal. It is a reference to measure the quality and quantity of potential chitosan nanoparticles as a sealer in endodontic treatment.

B. Preparation sample of tooth

A total of 30 mandibular premolars that had been extracted were immersed in saline solution and divided into three groups, Group A (epoxy resin sealer with irrigation of NaOCl 2,5 % + EDTA 17%, B (epoxy resin sealer with 1% Chitosan nanoparticles and Irrigation of NaCl 2.5 % + nano chitosan high molecule 0.1%), C (epoxy resin sealer with 2% Chitosan nanoparticles and Irrigation of NaCl 2.5 % + nano chitosan high molecule 0.2%). Each group consisted of 6 dental samples. Furthermore, all samples were cut with a disc bur on the crown of the teeth and the cemento-enamel junction boundary with the help of a bur. Next, endodontic treatment modeling was carried out. Each sample was measured for tooth length to determine the working distance. Root canals were negotiated to apical patency and working length using file #10. Then, the initial irrigation of 5 mL of irrigation solution was carried out. Then the root canal was prepared using a crown down technique using a Protaper Gold rotary instrument file and an endo motor speed of 300 rpm. The root canal preparation was started with file S1, followed by files S2, F1, and F2 according to the working length. 3 mL, while for the final irrigation, it is given 5 mL of irrigation solution for 1 minute. Then the root canals were dried using paper points. Furthermore, according to a predetermined group, the root canal was obturated with guttapercha and a sealer (Sornkul and Stannard, 1992).

C. Sealer Penetration Assay

The sealer penetration test into the dentinal tubules used a dye approach with 2% Methylene Blue. The samples made endodontic treatment. The teeth were coated with nail polish twice over the entire sample surface, except for 1mm at the apical portion. The samples were put into test tubes according to their respective groups, adding 5 mL of 2% Methylene Blue. Then incubated at 37 °C for 48 hours and allowed to stand for 15 at room temperature. A total of 150 L of dye was put in a 96 Well Plate, then examined at 515 nm OD spectrophotometry. Methylene Blue color change indicates dye penetration activity in dentinal tubules (Souza et al., 2009).

D. Scanning Electron Microscope of Root Canal

Examination of the adhesive sealer on the root canal wall was examined by SEM (Scanning Electron Microscope). The treatment started by cutting the tooth crown longitudinally

from the cemento-enamel junction to the tip of the apex. The sample was cleaned to remove dirt and form a good sample surface structure, then polished. Afterward, the samples were examined using an SEM tool (Hitachi TM 3000, Japan). The samples were placed in a vacuum chamber in the SEM and performed at 1200x, 1500x, and 2000x magnification. For 1500x magnification, the image will be divided into nine observation areas assessed using the scoring method through double-blind observations by two different people. They measured the level of density (adhesive) of the sealer on the root canal wall (Virdee et al., 2018). Qualitative data from SEM images were analyzed descriptively.

E. Statistical Analyses

The absorption and penetration data between the epoxy and chitosan nanoparticle sealer groups were analyzed by a Simple T-test. The comparison data between the treatment groups were examined by One Way Anova with a limit of the significance of $p < 0.05$ and $r = 1$, and there was a strong relationship.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Figure 1, it is shown that the epoxy sealer group with the addition of 1% chitosan nanoparticles had better adhesion to the root canal than the other groups. The indication is that there is an increase in the penetration of the sealer in the root canal and a decrease in the absorption value. The reduction in sealer absorption indicates that the sealer penetration into the root canal has been evenly distributed.

Fig. 1:- The adhesive power of sealer and chitosan nanoparticles in root canals. The absorption and penetration of methylene blue in the root canal as a reference for the adhesive strength of the sealer in the root canal. A (epoxy resin sealer), B (epoxy resin sealer with 1% Chitosan nanoparticles), C (epoxy resin sealer with 2% Chitosan nanoparticles). Bar (Adhesive sealer) Bar Error (Standard error)

Figure 2 shows the sealer density. Line 1, (a) sealer and (b) residual smear layer. Both images show the sealer density with the root canal wall and the presence of a residual smear layer. Line 2, (a) SEM profile of root canal density sealer with the addition of 1% chitosan, which adapts well to the entire

root canal wall. Line 3, (a) remaining guttapercha attached to the sealer with 2% chitosan. (b) microleakage between sealer with 2% chitosan on the root canal wall. Based on the adhesion, the sealer with adding 1% chitosan had better adaptability in increasing the adhesive on the root canal.

Fig.2:- SEM profile of adhesive sealer in root canals. Line 1 (Root canal with epoxy sealer). Line 2. (Root canals treated with epoxy sealer with 1% Chitosan nanoparticles). Line 3 (Root canals treated with epoxy sealer with Chitosan nanoparticles 2%). 200x (left) and 1500x (right) magnification

Based on the sample test, the T. test showed a significant difference in sealer absorption ($p < 0.05$; 0.04) and sealer penetration ($p < 0.05$; 0.003). The intensity of absorption and penetration has a relatively strong relationship ($r = 0.79$). One Way Anova analysis data between the absorption and penetration groups had a significant relationship ($p < 0.005$; 0.001) with a strong relationship ($r = 0.89$).

This study evaluated the potential of high molecular chitosan nanoparticles combined with epoxy resin as a sealer in root canal treatment. Chitosan has been applied in dentistry as an antibacterial, anti-oxidant, and adhesive in tooth root canals. (Gutmann et al., 2010) Its use as a sealer in obturation treatment has become the choice of researchers to compare its effectiveness with sealers. Epoxy resins that are often used in dentistry, such as AH plus

In this study, it was reported that the epoxy sealer group added with 1% chitosan nanoparticles could increase the attachment to the root canal better, which indicated an increase in the penetration of the sealer in the root canal and a decrease in the absorption value of the sealer. (Image 1). Absorption of sealers and other materials is absorption which

means the uptake or transfer of substances into or through tissues or tubules, such as the biological removal of an extruded sealer (Fisher et al., 2008). The increase in sealer activity on the material depends on the strength of the absorption power of the sealer material when interacting with the adhesion opponent. The absorption of the sealer material is highly dependent on changes in time and the content of the adhesive compound. In addition, sealers play an essential role in repairing root canals of teeth (Skrtic and Antonucci, 2016).

Kim (2010) reported that using root canal sealers to provide adhesion can fill irregularities and minor differences between the core filling material and the root canal wall. In addition, the sealer also acts as a lubricant during the absorption adaptation process (Jang et al., 2010). Henston (2012) revealed that root canal sealers and other materials have the main determinants of adhesion, where each sealer. Its advantages and disadvantages. Like AH, plus, zinc oxide eugenol is the most commonly used sealer and is the standard in many studies for comparison with other sealers (Henston et al., 2012). The penetration of the sealer into the dentinal tubules can indicate the degree of smear layer shedding (Ernani et al., 2015 Puspita et al., 2017). The ability of the sealer to penetrate the dentinal tubules depends on many factors, such as humidity and temperature. In addition, the presence of a smear layer can serve as a barrier and prevent the penetration of the sealer into the dentinal tubules (Turner-Walker, 2008).

In this study, a root canal sealer containing a mixture of Chitosan and AH Plus resin was found to increase the penetration in dentin tubules of the root canal. General conditions such as Chitosan's pH, Chitosan, the chemical structure of Chitosan, and the type of ion can determine the interaction with other solutions (Aranaz et al., 2009). Chitosan has been used to repair bone and has proven to be one of the most promising dental biomaterials (Cheung et al., 2015). Another study on Chitosan in dentistry has been shown to reduce the microhardness of dentin when used as an irrigating solution in root canals, and the effect is more significant at higher concentrations (Ernani et al., 2015; Praveenet al., 2017).

The research results reported in Figure 2 are to study and observe the density and strength of the sealer, smear layer, microleakage, and root canal wall profile. The research results in the figure show that the AH Plus sealer can provide good density, but the SEM profile shows the presence of a smear layer. The smear layer that is formed is generally the remnant of the sealer interaction process with the dental material on the root canal wall because AH plus is not biodegradable, so the residual material tends to be scattered throughout the root canal wall with different morphological forms (Debelian and Trope, 2003). 2016). Endodontic irrigation influenced the effect of the smear layer development. The produce smear layer will help the growth of pathogenic bacteria and thus thwart root canal obturation (Zargar et al., 2015).

Ormiga (2016) and Rasendren (2021) compared the AH plus product with EndoREZ, both used as sealers in endodontic therapy. In contrast, EndoREZ presented a higher ability to fill the root canal system in conjunction with guttapercha when compared to AH Plus and Pulp Canal Sealer. (Ormiga et al.,

2016), but the addition of Chitosan can increase the strength of the push-out guttapercha bond ($p < 0.05$). (Aydin et al., 2016) From the results of the study, it was found that AH plus (epoxy resin) had a failure of adhesion and the formation of a sear layer associated with its attachment to the dentinal root (Fig. 2). the polymerization of the sealer interface sealer on the root canal wall may have been affected by oxygen which can inhibit the polymerization of the vinyl in the composite resin and 40-60% of the carbon bonds remain unsaturated (Franco et al., 2002).

Nunes (2008) reported that higher sealer flow would allow more significant contact with the target material (primary) and hence more outstanding mechanical interlocking with dentin (Nunes et al., 2008). An SEM study showed that primers were found in all thirds of the root canals (cervical, middle and apical), which reinforces the assertion that failures noted at the sealer/dentine interface were more likely to be related to the sealer and not to the primary application (Tay et al., 2005). In this study, Chitosan has an excellent effect as a sealer, this has something to do with its excellent biocompatibility, biodegradability, non-toxicity, and also has bio-adhesion (Silva et al., 2013).

IV. CONCLUSION

Epoxy resin sealer with the addition of 1% chitosan high molecule nanoparticle has excellent absorption and penetration properties in root canal walls, increasing adhesion to root canal walls.

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